

1 Extended Case Study on SIGMERGE vs. Raconteur

Figure 1 presents three additional examples that further contrast SIGMERGE and Raconteur. In Case 3, the command uses OpenSSL for encrypted communication and invokes sh to execute a payload. Raconteur provides a parameter-level interpretation of each argument, and the resulting Sigma rule can precisely detect the given command instance. However, the rule remains closely tied to the concrete command text. In contrast, SIGMERGE produces a rule that emphasizes the underlying behavior pattern, improving readability and potential extensibility by covering related command variants. This increased expressiveness also introduces stricter matching conditions, which may affect recall in practice.

Cases 4 and 5 show the effect of contextual assumptions. SIGMERGE relies on TTP labels from CTRs and treats these commands as benign when no surrounding incident context is present, so it does not generate attack descriptions or Sigma rules for them. Raconteur does not depend on such context and still provides complete command interpretations. These examples illustrate two complementary design choices: SIGMERGE focuses on context guided detection coverage, while Raconteur provides detailed command explanations even without broader threat information.

Fig. 1. Comparing how SIGMERGE’s attack descriptions and Raconteur’s command explanations influence downstream Sigma rule generation, with intermediate outputs shown.